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REFLECTIONS ON TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the work is to reflect on teaching in higher education, highlighting many setbacks and stagnations, as well as opportunities for promotion and growth of teachers. Therefore, we seek to create a brief characterization of the university education, which describes the initiatives carried out based on the capacity of the university professor and confirms with a group of professors the higher education projects that they carry out themselves and their own practice. in higher education. We adopt the reflections of theorists in the field of education, whose greatest interest cuts a view of the university education. In this sense, the main aspects of theory substantiated here include: the notion of teaching as an organic intellectual; the question of the social (dis)valuation of teachers; aspiration and satisfaction in work; education and continued teaching and legislation. These are the themes that guide the formulation of questions to the respondents, as well as the parameters for the evaluation of the responses.

Keywords: Superior teaching; Education and teaching; Training.

INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of technology, diverse readings and research, teachers have been seeking countless innovations. Education is a vast field, and sometimes educators feel limited. The lack of incentives, government support, that is, funds for that there are broad courses such as Postgraduate, Masters, Doctorate and Post Doctorate make it difficult for teachers to need to update and train.

It is known that educating is not an easy task, because educating is being able to transform the data obtained by the teacher, because when we realize the learning, we feel powerful, we grow effectively, we will never forget the memorized lines. For this, the continuous process of training is urgent. And it is about the entire process of training/education that we seek to hear from a group of teachers, most of whom work in higher education.

In this work we seek to achieve some objectives: (i) To verify, together with a group of university professors, what projections the professors make of themselves and their own practice in higher education . (ii) To reflect on teaching in higher education, highlighting both the setbacks and impasses, as well as the possibilities for advancement and growth of the professor. (iii) To make a brief characterization of university teaching. (iv) To evaluate, based on interviews, the vision that the professor has of himself and of the training process, from the initial phase to the academic environment.

In theoretical terms, we gathered reflections from renowned authors in the field of Educational Theory, with important considerations about higher education teaching in Brazil. The methodological procedures were configured based on responses given to a short questionnaire with four questions and we asked three colleagues to answer them. Based on this first group, we formulated a larger questionnaire with six other questions. With this set of six questions, we approached a group of 30 teachers and asked them to answer these questions. Only 11 of these teachers returned the completed questionnaire. To analyze the 66 responses received, and the nine responses we already had in hand, we established a parameter of responses, highlighted from the theoretical framework used. From there, we

tabulated the responses in order to verify to what extent the responses received reflected, to some extent, our theoretical parameters.

Aiming at better systematization and for reasons of space, the theoretical aspects that we highlight are included in excerpts, which form the basis of the parameters for our evaluation.

TEACHING AND HIGHER EDUCATION

The development of our corpus went through two stages. In the first stage, we prepared a short questionnaire with four questions and submitted it to three professors, all of whom had postgraduate degrees and worked in higher education. After these interviews, we realized that we had a very small sample size, given our objectives. We expanded the questionnaire to six questions and distributed it to a larger group of professors (around 30). Of these, only 11 responded to our request. Thus, our analysis is divided into two stages: analysis and tabulation of the responses from group I (first questionnaire), analysis and tabulation of the responses from group II (second questionnaire), and, finally, a general reflection on the responses obtained.

As for the questions in Group I, in addition to being fewer in number (only four), one of these questions is different from those in Group II. These two differences – one in relation to the sampling and the other in relation to the difference in the question – led us to make a separate tabulation for each group.

Analysis of group I

In the first group of interviewees, there was no concern about requesting personal data; only the level of academic training and the segment of higher education teaching were asked. All had postgraduate degrees and were university professors. Here is the first profile:

TABLE I: INTERVIEWEE PROFILE – Group I

Level of Performance	Institution where you work	
	Public	Private
1-Higher education		X
2-Higher education		X
3-Higher education	X	X

Our analysis strategy is, based on the question, to seek parameters for the answers in the theoretical assumptions focused on here and to record in tables whether the answers are close to our parameters [yes], whether they do not correspond to the expected answers [no], or whether they are somewhere in between [+ OR -]. This type of tabulation, in fact, corresponds to the type of answer given by the teachers, often monosyllabic, as was the case with many of the answers from GROUP II. When the answers are discursivized, the tabulation criterion changes.

Let's move on to the first tabulation.

(1) WHAT IS THE ROLE OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS IN ACADEMIC EDUCATION?

Parameter for response:

To be able to 'act otherwise' means to be able to intervene in the world, or to refrain from such intervention, with the effect of influencing a specific process or state of affairs. This presupposes that to be an agent is to be able to display (...) a range of causal powers, including that of influencing those displayed by others. Action depends on the individual's ability to 'make a difference' to a pre-existing state of affairs or course of events. An agent ceases to be an agent if the ability to 'make a difference' is lost. (GIDDENS, 1989:11)

The parameter we sought sought to avoid 'classical' responses, which would reaffirm that the pedagogical process is extremely important in teacher training. When we speak of academic training, we are talking about a projection in different directions, both in the training of the teacher himself, and in the training of his future students. In this case, it seemed pertinent to us to choose the above statement because of some statements: capacity to act in another way - that is, the teacher is not seen or accepted as a mere reproducer of content; capacity to act also presupposes the figure of an agent capable of 'creating a difference'. In this sense, the teacher, with the capacity to act reflexively, must create, in the daily practice and together with other

professionals, conditions to leave the "role" of lesser value attributed to him. (CALDERANO, 2006)

TABLE II: PROJECTION OF PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE IN ACADEMIC TRAINING - Group I

ANSWERS	YES	NO	+ OR -
The pedagogical process is a <i>sine qua non condition</i> . [...] which aims at interaction between people. In the case of teaching, this interaction is notable because it only exists when one is aware of what one wants to transmit, how one wants to transmit it and to whom one wants to transmit it. The need for permanent evaluation on the part of the teacher.	X		
The pedagogical process is what will give rise to education, and it is an inconceivable reading required of it today. School must be a welcoming and pleasant environment, providing students with access, permanence, and successful and quality learning, regardless of their physical, cognitive, social, or cultural characteristics.		X	
The pedagogical process is important in academic training, because we need it to be able to achieve our goals in the classroom.		X	

The answers above tell us little about what the role of the pedagogical process would be, except for the first one. The first answer understands this process as an interaction between people, aimed at the awareness of what one wants to transmit, as well as to whom and in what way this content is transmitted. Although the verb 'transmit' was used, there is a concern in discerning the agents involved in the action of teaching, from which we can assume that the answer comes close to our parameter: capacity to act in another way and capacity to act also presupposes the figure of an agent capable of 'creating a difference'.

As for the other answers, they are circular and merely qualifying, without providing a clear definition of what would be expected. The pedagogical process must be enjoyable so that learning is successful and of high quality, without discriminating against any type of student. Finally, it is redundant to state that the pedagogical process is important.

(2) SHOULD TEACHERS SEEK NEW TRAINING METHODS? JUSTIFY.

Parameter for the response:

Teachers must always be changing with the community around them, making it worthwhile to understand any decline in the descending scale of teaching and learning. This focus on the power of action - whether of teachers, organic

intellectuals, course participants or other social subjects – becomes necessary here, because it is understood that any principle, political project or methodological proposal filled with the best intentions and content tends to fail if there are no concrete people, historical subjects willing to analyze it, reflect on it, verify the possibilities of its concreteness, make necessary adaptations, putting their mark, their style, their vigor in the achievement of those greater objectives.

The lack of training of professionals interferes with their daily performance. Professional growth is devastating when they expose what they intend to pass on to their class. What does not mean is that they abandon the educational process, but that they demonstrate the truthfulness of their purpose as an education professional, acting with capacity and determination to work in different institutions and in the transformation of learning, and with values that affect the structure of citizens, enriching their social and political environment. (CALDERANO & LOPES, 2006)

What interests us most in the above excerpt, a parameter for question two, is to verify that training is not restricted to the teacher's involvement in taking new specific courses. Training first involves an assessment of the environment in which the teacher operates, detecting progress and setbacks. It is therefore a matter of thinking about training based on a diagnosis of the reality of each school, and the reality of the classroom. Once this diagnosis is made, the veracity of the purpose of each education professional would be on the agenda.

TABLE III: PROJECTION OF CONTINUING EDUCATION – Group I

ANSWERS	YES	NO
Yes: "Times change. Ideas change." (Camões). And teachers are the driving force behind the civilizing process.	X	
Yes: the teacher is the agent who will provide favorable learning conditions in the classroom for all students, respecting their needs and particularities, and must always be open to "Learning to Learn".	X	
Yes: teachers must be constantly updated, especially nowadays when there are many new technologies that need to be used in the classroom.	X	

All teachers recognize the need for ongoing training in a constant process of updating to meet

the demands that reach the school, both in terms of new theoretical principles and the acceptance of new technological instruments to be adopted.

(3) THE TEACHER LIKES TO EVALUATE, BUT DOES NOT LIKE TO BE EVALUATED. DO YOU AGREE?

Parameter for the response:

Teacher training presupposes that, in their training process, they build investigative skills, assume a critical-reflective stance towards themselves, others and their teaching practice, and become a professional capable of opening themselves to knowledge from experience, to their uniqueness, to the concerns and worries of the unknown, of the different and the unequal. (FOG, 1995)

Assessment, in general, is not a topic discussed when focusing on teacher training. Assessment is almost always limited to giving grades and concepts to students. In this case, the teacher does not insert himself into the assessment process as a target of the assessment, nor does he usually admit that he himself is reflected in the assessment result. The parameter above goes beyond what is understood by 'assessment'. The relationship between assessment and training is immediately established, from which the meaning of assessment as 'a critical-reflective stance towards oneself, others and one's teaching practice' derives.

TABLE IV: PROJECTION OF THE EVALUATION PROCESS – Group I

ANSWERS	YES	NO
Yes: but I recognize that there is an evaluation of the Teacher, but it is not random, without criteria, made by any student. Selection of functioning students, with a good performance index in the subjects taught. Evaluating a teacher requires outgoing behaviors and certain criteria that are not within the reach of all students, regardless of how much they like or hate the teacher. The most important thing: the teacher, with his self-awareness, does not abstain from this evaluation. If everything is possible in the evaluation of the Student, and the Student does not change his behavior in any way, why does the Teacher have to be perfect?	X	
Yes: teacher evaluation is not a simple task. As supervisors who, for decades, have promoted the initial and ongoing training of our teachers to evaluate teachers can attest to. [Evaluation] requires special personal and professional characteristics, in addition to specialized training and hundreds of hours of training, dedicated to observing classes and recording incidents predicted there. Those who have been prepared to evaluate students are not [...] automatically prepared to evaluate themselves.	X	
Yes: nobody likes to be evaluated.	X	

In the three answers above, there is a point of agreement regarding 'not liking to be evaluated'. But, with the exception of the third answer, two aspects of evaluation are at stake within the expression 'who evaluates whom'.

The content of the first response clearly points to a defensive position on the part of the teacher, who admits being evaluated, but not by any student because "Evaluating a teacher requires outgoing behaviors and certain criteria that are not within the reach of all students, regardless of how much they like or hate the teacher." In other words, only some students know/can evaluate. This projection certainly points to the one who is always well evaluated and who, due to a relationship of reciprocity, would evaluate the teacher in the same way.

In the second response, the sphere of assessment does not immediately involve the student. Once again, we are faced with a defensive stance on the part of the teacher in relation to the figure of professionals with the role of 'supervisors', who were busy inspecting the progress of the pedagogical work and offering suggestions and strategies to be applied in the classroom. Further on, he admits, very clearly, that 'those who were prepared to assess students are not automatically prepared to assess themselves'.

Ultimately, what this small sample reveals is that those who evaluate do not like to be evaluated, nor do they like to evaluate themselves. This concept of evaluation is in no way similar to the concept present in our parameter.

(4) WHAT IS THE IMPORTANCE OF CURRENT LEGISLATION (LDB – GUIDELINES AND BASES LAW) IN THE CURRENT PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS?

Parameter for the response:

In 1996, Brazil united its academic body in different areas and with the approval of federal law 9394 of December 20, 1996, which gave a new guideline to Brazilian education, very well founded in its article 92, revoked the laws mentioned above.

As of January 1, 1997, public and private universities became technically and legally autonomous in managing their education systems.

The evolution of higher education began to diversify in the 1960s, with the approval of Federal Law No. 4024 of December 20, 1961 (LDB). In 1968, Federal Law No. 5540 of December 28, 1968 was approved. This law dealt exclusively with higher education. This advancement meant that public and private education institutions had to adapt to a new education system provided for in articles 43 to 57 of the current LDB (LDB 9394/96).

The Law of Guidelines and Bases (LDB) was – and still is – considered an important milestone in education legislation in Brazil, especially with regard to higher education, giving autonomy to educational institutions to manage their pedagogical projects.

TABLE V: PROJECTION OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT LAWS – Group I

ANSWERS
The LDB is the LDB. In my opinion, it should be something serious and stable. Changes should only be made when necessary and not according to the momentary whims of government policy. In countries where education is a priority, the foundations that have worked have been maintained for decades and even centuries, as is the case in France, where principles originating from the Napoleonic Code are still being used, and in Germany, with Bismarck's initiatives.
The LDB must invest in education, there is no doubt about that, but where is the investment in teaching professionals included? Political campaigns do not mention pedagogues as a priority. We fight for an equal and democratic education.
The LDB created parameters that must be followed throughout Brazil. I believe that this reduces inequalities.

Despite the importance of the LDB, few teachers have taken the time to read the law in its entirety and become aware of its content. All that is known is that it is a law, but its scope in the pedagogical process is unknown. This fact can be proven by the answers above, which are of a generic nature, as they do not refer to any specific aspect of the LDB.

Analysis of group II

We now have a group of 11 teachers who responded to our survey. This group answered 10 questions, four of which were about identifying data about the participants. The first organization of our data from Group II, as in Group I, proceeded to a general table (Table VI), mapping the profile of the interviewees in their entirety: 11 teachers.

TABLE VI: INTERVIEWEE PROFILE - Group II

Level of Performance	Institution where you work		Time of operation
	Public	Private	
1-Higher education		X	30 years
2-Higher education	X	X	17 years old
3-Higher education	X	X	30 years
4-Higher education		X	15 years
5-Higher education		X	41 years old
6-Higher education	X	X	7 years
7-Higher education		X	12 years
8-Higher education	X	X	35 years old
9- Basic Education and Higher Education		X	40 years
10- Basic Education and Higher Education	X	X	28 years old 19 years old
11- Basic Education and Higher Education	X	X	25 years 3 years

Next, we explored the responses of the 11 teachers. These are listed one by one and accompanied by the responses of this group (total: 6 questions and 66 responses). After analyzing these responses, based on parameters based on theoretical assumptions, we made a critical analysis of the responses illustrated in a tabulation for each question (Tables VII to XII). When the questions coincide with those of Group I, the parameters of the responses are the same.

Six questions and sixty-six answers

(5) HOW DO YOU SEE YOURSELF AS A HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHER?

Parameter for response:

The teaching being in the process of continuing education is understood here as an organic intellectual, in the Gramscian sense: All men are intellectuals. In any physical work, even the most mechanical and disaggregated, there is a minimum of technical qualification, there is a minimum of creative intellectual activity.
(Luckesi et al, 1991)

The choice of this parameter seemed quite pertinent to us, in the sense that, in Gramsci's terms, the creative intellectual capacity is what defines each and every human being. This definition also moves away from the notion of a teacher as someone whose task would be to transmit content.

TABLE VII: PROJECTION OF HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS – Group II

ANSWERS	YES	NO	+ OR -
Fully accomplished			X
Student Encouragement / Practice for Teaching Purposes	X		
Good teacher and helpless		X	
Enjoys interacting with students			X
Happy and willing to train the student	X		
Knowledge transferor		X	
Privilege of being able to combine teaching and research	X		
Professional in constant learning	X		
Did not respond	---	---	---
Committed to highlighting the importance of higher education in social tasks	X		
Higher education requires constant research, reading and continuing education. Building an environment that is conducive to the construction of knowledge by students, encouraging them to always seek ethical and professional commitment.	X		

In addition to promoting mediation between individuals and society, teaching should seek to keep in mind as a work goal the fact that a group of men and women does not “distinguish” itself and does not become independent “by itself” without organizing itself, and there is no organization without intellectuals, that is, without organizers and leaders” (Gramsci, 1986). By taking this definition as a parameter for analyzing the answers above, we see that the teacher is not fully aware of his projection as an organic intellectual. Fifty percent of the answers fully cover the need to manage and be managed, often seeing himself only as a manager of knowledge.

In this regard, Campos (2006) argues that it is urgent to create the necessary conditions for teachers to move from their traditional “role” of “curriculum instrumentalists” to “authors and protagonists as a guarantee that schools and classes are real scenarios for educational transformations”. This is a brief profile of the organic intellectual. This pedagogical action, far from being reduced to a teaching relationship, assuming “teachers and students”, must be based on an organic, non-bureaucratic relationship, highlighting the dialectical character of a transformative educational action where the “educator must be educated” (Marx and Engels, 1986, apud COUTINHO, 1981).

(6) IS THERE A DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PRACTICE IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION AND HIGHER EDUCATION?

Parameter for response:

Teachers in the contemporary world experience a great need for a high cultural index, which will underpin their professional life. This index is continuous from the first years of teaching until their formation in the academic world. Therefore, practices must be differentiated and worked on, with the conviction that each student has their own way of learning. (CALDERANO, 2006)

TABLE VIII: PROJECTION OF TEACHING PRACTICE AT DIFFERENT LEVELS – Group II

ANSWERS	YES	NO	+ OR -
I think so	X		
Yes	X		
Yes: it differs in psychological approach	X		
I only work in higher education	---	---	---
Yes: in higher education, students should be trained to study without so much support from teachers.	X		
Yes: the maturity of students is different	X		
Yes: at higher education level, the teacher generally teaches subjects related to the area of specialization.	X		
I don't know about elementary school	---	---	---
Yes: there is a need to respect the intellectual development of each age group.	X		
Yes: as a basic education teacher, I had to adapt the content to the needs of the students. In higher education, it is different: I see the student as responsible for the Education of the present and the future, based on the three pillars – Teaching, Research and Extension. Shifting the emphasis from teaching to learning, highlighting the need for interdisciplinarity and teamwork.	X		
Yes: there is a difference in the way people express themselves and in their teaching practices. In basic education, the goal should be to educate citizens. In professional education, the goal should be to enter the job market and to educate people about ethics in any profession.	X		

The answers above categorically state that basic/elementary education is different from higher education: only two of the answers above indicate that they are unaware of the difference between these two pedagogical practices. But where does this difference lie, as attested by the other nine interviewees? Unlike the previous percentage, we consider that only three of the interviewees come close to the parameter outlined for the question at hand, excluding the laconic answers. The Law of Guidelines and Bases itself foresees the differences between these levels in pedagogical practice, in the sense of adapting the content to the characteristics of the different groups of students in the basic education phase,

of thinking about professional training already in the specialized education phase, but, above all, not losing sight of the fact that these are continuous paths.

Academia should focus primarily on training professionals, aiming not only at transmitting knowledge but also at practicing professionally. These are guidelines that seem to be lost in higher education. There is almost always a disconnect between what is theoretically advocated and how to put into practice – regardless of the educational level – all the accumulated theories. This disconnect is fully reflected in the answers above, when the majority of the professionals interviewed seem oblivious to the task of teaching, and how it is done. Once again, the professional is portrayed as a “mere transmitter of content”.

(7) DURING YOUR MASTERS/ DOCTORATE COURSE, DID YOU ACQUIRE ALL THE KNOWLEDGE AND “TOOLS” TO PRACTICE THE PROFESSION OF HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHER?

Parameter for response:

Teachers in the contemporary world experience a great need for a high level of knowledge, which will support their professional lives. This level is continuous from the first years of teaching until their formation in the academic world. (CALDERANO, 2006: 36) Therefore, practices must be differentiated and worked on, with the conviction that each student has their own way of learning. In addition to recognizing the concepts of continuing teacher training, teachers must reflect on its dimensions, axes and challenges, engaging in the debate on the importance of constructing effective proposals that aim at the quality of the public provision of basic education in Brazil and the possibilities of establishing teacher training policies that articulate the different education systems and the university. (DALBEN, 2006)

TABLE IX: PROJECTION OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING – Group II

ANSWERS	YES	NO	+ OR -
As far as engineering goes, yes.	X		
No		X	
Not necessarily		X	
No: in practice there is no training		X	
No: just a few		X	
No		X	

No		X	
No: there are always new things to learn		X	
No: the knowledge and tools offered are not sufficient for the exercise of the profession; but they constitute the basis for practical application for academic training.			X
Yes: in general. It presented me with tools to know where and how to look for new ways to pass on knowledge.	X		
No: just as the degree did not fully qualify me to work as a teacher in basic education.		X	

The responses to question (7), in which only two percent positively attest, to a certain extent, to what postgraduate courses offer as tools for their teaching practice, clearly reaffirm what was suggested in the responses to the previous question (6): the elision between theorized knowledge and the reality of teaching practice. The content of these two responses (6) and (7) goes beyond what was expected – in this case, “the debate on the importance of constructing effective proposals that aim at the quality of the public provision of basic education in Brazil and the possibilities of establishing teacher training policies that articulate the different education systems and the university” –, because the argumentative content of the responses to both questions (in (6) and in (7)) seems insufficient to us. One interviewee restricts the positive value of his training to his area of interest, in this case, engineering. Here, the notion of the teacher as an organic intellectual is lost. The other interviewee modalizes the answer with the expression “in general”: the academy only offers some instruments so that the teacher can seek continued training himself.

(8) WHAT IS THE ROLE OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS IN ACADEMIC TRAINING?

Parameter for the response:

To be able to ‘act otherwise’ means to be able to intervene in the world, or to refrain from such intervention, with the effect of influencing a specific process or state of affairs. This presupposes that to be an agent is to be able to display (...) a range of causal powers, including that of influencing those displayed by others. Action depends on the individual’s ability to ‘make a difference’ to a pre-existing state of affairs or course of events. An agent ceases to be an agent and the ability to ‘make a difference’, that is, to exercise some kind of power, is lost. (GIDDENS, 1989)

TABLE X: PROJECTION OF PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE IN THE LEARNING PROCESS – group

TT	ANSWERS
	It is of utmost importance.
	Your role is to teach and learn.
	Irrelevant.
	He didn't answer.
	Fundamental role in the construction of the course.
	Important, but very bad as addressed today.
	He didn't answer.
	For those who want to be a teacher it is very important.
	Offer instruments for the use of the appropriate Methodology to improve academic training.
	Essential: offering guidelines for the teacher to teach classes, with methodologies, appropriate resources and bibliography inherent to the discipline.
	The importance of the pedagogical subjects offered in the undergraduate course is important. These are the subjects that make us think about our future pedagogical work and show us the way. However, the role and influence of the teacher of these subjects in the training of the future professional is recognized.

What can be seen from the answers above is, on the one hand, the recognition that the pedagogical process is important in professional training. But to what is this importance attributed? The answers presented – 8 only out of a universe of 11 interviewees – are vague, limiting themselves to saying that the pedagogical process is, in fact, important. They are tautological answers, which do not reflect any reflection of the individual, but merely endorse the content of the question, with the exception of the last answer. This outlines the horizon of the pedagogical process as a process for “future pedagogical practice and that shows us paths.” This statement reflects much of the parameter for this question: being able to ‘act differently’ means being able to intervene in the world, or refrain from such intervention, with the effect of influencing a specific process or state of affairs.

(9) SHOULD TEACHERS SEEK NEW TRAINING METHODS? JUSTIFY.

Parameter for the response:

Teachers must always be changing with the community around them, making it worthwhile to understand any decline in the descending scale of teaching and learning. This focus on the power of action – whether of teachers, organic intellectuals, course participants or other social subjects – becomes necessary here, because it is understood that any principle, political project or methodological proposal filled with the best intentions and content tends to fail if there are no concrete people, historical subjects willing to analyze it, reflect on it, verify the possibilities of its concreteness, make necessary adaptations, putting their mark, their style, their vigor in the achievement of those greater objectives. The lack of training of professionals interferes

with their daily performance. Professional growth is devastating when they expose what they intend to pass on to their class. What does not mean is that they abandon the educational process, but that they demonstrate the truthfulness of their purpose as an education professional, acting with capacity and determination to work in different institutions and in the transformation of learning, and with values that affect the structure of citizens, enriching their social and political environment. (CALDERANO & LOPES, 2006)

Parameter for the response:

In 1996, Brazil united its academic body in different areas and with the approval of federal law 9394 of December 20, 1996, which gave a new guideline to Brazilian education, very well founded in its article 92, revoked the laws mentioned above.

As of January 1, 1997, public and private universities became technically and legally autonomous in managing their education systems.

The evolution of higher education began to diversify in the 1960s, with the approval of Federal Law No. 4024 of December 20, 1961 (LDB). In 1968, Federal Law No. 5540 of December 28, 1968 was approved. This law dealt exclusively with higher education. This advancement meant that public and private education institutions had to adapt to a new education system provided for in articles 43 to 57 of the current LDB (LDB 9394/96).

TABLE XI: PROJECTION OF CONTINUING EDUCATION – group II

ANSWERS	YES	NO
Without a doubt: when it comes to engineering, I think it is fundamental	X	
Yes: students and teachers have new and different learning needs. Teachers need to keep up to date.	X	
Always: advancement of knowledge and continuous change of paradigms.	X	
Yes, always: due to the fact that education is an activity in constant change.	X	
Yes: make classes dynamic.	X	
Yes: educational technologies change all the time.	X	
Yes: ongoing participation in an evaluation process.	X	
Yes: several advances deserve to be incorporated.	X	
Yes: the world of knowledge is constantly progressing. Need for updating.	X	
Always: in study groups, at Congresses, Forums, etc.	X	
Yes: awareness that learning is continuous. Knowledge is always renewed, just as human beings are in a constant process of construction. Pedagogical activity requires research, creation, evaluation and reconstruction.	X	

The key to understanding the answers above – all of which are affirmative – lies in the fact that they all present creativity and engagement in the educational process as a possible solution to the problems faced in teaching. Becoming a protagonist, highlighting one's social importance, is possible for teachers, and a viable path to this is through training. In addition to helping teachers professionally, in the sense of adding formal content, it also helps them as citizens, because it encourages them to reflect on their practices. Everyone recognizes the importance of ongoing training, but the question is: will teachers have working conditions that allow them to constantly seek professional improvement?

TABLE XII: PROJECTION OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT LAWS – group II

ANSWERS
Globalization requires compatibility between nations. A great degree of freedom between nations does not seem appropriate.
I don't know the LDB.
It only serves to get in the way in most cases and points.
Standardize and make the process uniform throughout the country.
Serve as a basis for building a pedagogical process.
I don't think it will have the desired effect. The IDEB is a mess and we should learn from our Chilean brothers who have an economy similar to Brazil's and a much more advanced education system.
Most important for elementary and high school education.
Normative. Guidelines that encourage the implementation of practices in HEIs [educational institutions].
Need for legislation that accompanies development to monitor changes that regulate the pedagogical process.
The LDB has already been significantly modified. Professionals need to be aware of these modifications.
It represented an important step forward in guaranteeing educational rights to all Brazilian citizens. Knowing the LDB is essential for practicing the profession.

(10) WHAT IS THE IMPORTANCE OF CURRENT LEGISLATION (LDB – GUIDELINES AND BASES LAW) IN THE CURRENT PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS?

Of the 11 responses given above, only the last one reveals that she is actually familiar with the LDB. The other responses are full of evasive and even meaningless comments regarding the goals set forth in the aforementioned law. The LDB aimed, above all, at reforming the curricular proposals and parameters with a view to greater democratization of education, seeking to facilitate

access by the lower classes to various levels of education. In short, they are education professionals, but they are unaware of the laws that govern this practice. This fact is also recorded above with the responses from GROUP I.

A general summary of the responses analyzed here highlights many of the factors that support the statement about a profession that, while facing a crisis, still relies on the permanence of the profession's prestige, as stated by Nóvoa (1995). This crisis is due to the feeling of devaluation of the profession, which often faces precarious working conditions, low salaries, and a lack of government policies that truly invest in the quality of education. All of this stems from the contradiction between the ideal image of the profession and the concrete reality that teachers face on a daily basis.

One fact, however, is consensual among all interviewees: the need for ongoing training, for frequent training/updating. But how can this important stage in teacher training be achieved? How can the ideal be transformed into reality? How can good training be fully achieved? Only by raising awareness of this need in educational institutions, opening doors and investing in study centers within the institutions themselves, thus facilitating exchanges between peers and ultimately investing in the formation of organic intellectuals.

CONCLUSION

In our journey, we took as a central guideline to verify to what extent the higher education teacher would see himself as an "organic intellectual", one who is always interacting with other professionals and with students and, above all, does not see himself as a mere manager of knowledge, without allowing himself to be managed. Since the intellectual and creative capacity is inherent to each and every human being, such statements, far from being mere theoretical meanings, add implications of a professional, political and ideological nature. They add projections of the subject-teacher, of his "to-do's", of his practice and of those with whom this subject relates.

What projections were reflected in our work?

From the sample as a whole, a small portion of the interviewees – around 1% – would be close

to an ideal teacher. In the remaining percentage, the image of an organic intellectual clearly slides towards the image of a manager – a professional concerned, above all, with transmitting, within a given curricular structure, the programmatic contents. This "teacher -manager" does not stop to question the effectiveness of this type of pedagogical practice. This position was quite reflected when the interviewees pointed out that being a primary school teacher is different from being a higher education teacher, because the university student has the autonomy to learn on his own (?).

Another implication arising from these views is the split that is established between academic theorizing and the confrontation of everyday school life. Eighty percent of the interviewees responded that the university does not offer sufficient training for acting as a teacher. These are teachers who confirm that the "training process" is important, but do not know how to explain exactly where this "importance" lies. This is a tautological stance, as they endorse the content of the question itself.

We are also facing a university that we do not want, in the sense that teachers do not feel well prepared. The responses to questions (3) and (5) – about whether the university offers sufficient training for classroom practice and the importance of seeking new means of training – reached quite significant percentages: ninety percent responded that in higher education they did not receive sufficient training to face the classroom and ninety percent stated the need for ongoing training. These percentages reaffirm, on the one hand, the deficient university that is offered to us and, on the other, because this university has deficiencies, the need for constant improvement.

Another impasse. Everyone confirms that continuing education is necessary, but at the same time, they also point out that working conditions rarely favor the pursuit of ongoing specialization. There is a lack of resources to participate in conferences and seminars; there is a lack of cohesion in work groups to engage in research. These are all things that the university has not been offering.

In short, in general terms, we have found that there is a great distance in our journey between

the parameters based on renowned education theorists and the projections reflected in the responses of those who work in higher education. We did not work with a large group – we only interviewed 14. But what can we say about the fact that we approached more than 30 professionals and only less than half were willing to answer us? The non-saying is present, however, in both positions, both in the silent responses of those who did not return the questions and in the evasive, laconic answers.

Where is the face of the organic intellectual hidden?

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